

OpenWebSearch.EU

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search
Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital
Sovereignty”

**Deliverable D4.3 Report of
privacy, transparency, and trust
models for search applications V2**

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

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ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
IT4I@VSB	Technical University of Ostrava
CERN	Organisation européenne pour la recherche nucléaire
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
CSC	Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy (IT Center for Science)
NLNET	Stichting NLnet
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
SUMA-EV	SuMa e.V. - Verein für freien Wissenszugang (Associated Partner)

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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document describes the deliverable D4.3 “Report of privacy, transparency, and trust models for search applications V2” of the OpenWebSearch.eu project funded by the EC under the GA 101070014 within the Horizon Europe Framework programme. It reports on models on privacy, trust, transparency, and search paradigms related to search applications.

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vii. Executive Summary

According to the work package description, this deliverable is dedicated to the privacy, transparency, and trust models (Task 4.4 and 4.5). A trust and transparency model is outlined in Section 3 that describes how to foster trust of the user in search engines, but also raises research questions on the relation between trust and transparency. A privacy model is described in Section 4 that explains how to maintain user data without violating data protection needs. This model is created along the design of the location-based search application and will be further elaborated as part of the development of this application.

1. Introduction

One of the key goals of the OpenWebSearch.eu (OWS) project is the creation of an Open Web Index (OWI) that enables the development of various types of applications using web data. Work package 4 aims to support the development of vertical search engines (search applications) that consumes index data retrieved from the OWI. In contrast to general purpose and large-scale search engines, such as Google or Microsoft Bing, vertical search engines serve specific domains or purposes, which also provides opportunities to optimize search and retrieval strategies. The reason for providing support methods is grounded in another key goal of OWS, which is the building of an ecosystem of vertical search engines and other applications based on OWS.

This deliverable is dedicated to the creation of models for privacy, transparency and trust. These models are designed for the use of OWS search applications, in order to increase the user experience and meet user expectations. The trust and transparency model outlines how to foster trust of the user and is ready to be included and applied by any search applications. The privacy model describes how to maintain user data without violating data protection needs. This model is created along the development of the location-based search application (see D4.1).

While deliverable D4.1 focuses on technical aspects of search application development, human-centred aspects are in the focus of this deliverable. The models are designed in a way that they can be integrated in other search applications. A report on further refinement of the models and how they are applied in search application will be provided in the final deliverable D4.4.

2. Search Paradigms

This section investigates different search paradigms, in order to outline relevant aspects of search engines related to OWS. These paradigms are not mutually exclusive, but are partially overlapping. They also highlight new ways of retrieving information through open web search, increasing trust, and protecting privacy in contrast to features of classical search engines.

2.1 General Search

General search refers to the global search over an entire index that captures a large portion of the web (such as Google web search). Key challenges of general search is the vast size of the index and the ranking. The creation and storage of an index that contains most of the web needs enormous resources. The ranking of documents requires efficient algorithms and significant hardware resources to deliver relevant resources on top of the search result.

OWS will provide an open web index that can be used by front-ends and search applications to enable search for end-users. On the one hand, it is unlikely that OWS can compete with companies such as Google or Bing, regarding ranking and relevance of search results. On the other hand, OWS provides an open index that can be accessed directly and enables applications to perform own selection and ranking. In contrast to Google, that provides restrictions on changing the search result for external applications, OWS offers content-extracted and quality metadata and encourages the adaptation of search results to meet users' requirements.

2.2 Vertical Search Engines

In contrast to general purpose and large-scale search engines, such as Google or Bing, OWS shares the web index for vertical search engines serving specific domains or purposes, which also provides opportunities to optimize search and retrieval strategies. This results in particular benefits for the end user by offering higher precision of the search result, utilisation of domain knowledge in terms of ontologies or knowledge graphs, and facilitating specific user tasks. Today's popular and powerful vertical search solutions mostly pursue commercial purposes or are part of enterprises' business models, such as product search of Amazon, people search of LinkedIn, or hotel search of Booking.com. Even Google maintains vertical search engines (e.g. YouTube) and is interested in further vertical search solution as recently demonstrated through the purchase of the ITA Travel Search Company¹. Presently, vertical search engines become a more and more active field for commercial purposes, such as marketing, product vending, awareness capturing.

In order to enable the development of search verticals, OWS enables to download a portion or subset of the index related to a certain topic or geographical region. This allows to create a search application that makes use of this index subset and provides search features dedicated to its purpose and user expectations. Instead of dealing with a large index that makes it expensive to retrieve relevant search results, a small index makes it easier to perform accurate ranking. Furthermore, the index subset can be stored and managed on an own server, which increases the independence from external technologies. This enables 3rd party search applications without crawling Web sites and re-use partitions of the OWS index, and therefore reducing network traffic.

2.3 Personal Search

As the internet and accessible content continues to grow exponentially, the ability to quickly and accurately find relevant information has become increasingly important. However, as the volume of data on the internet increases, these search engines are starting to show their limitations. Artificial intelligence (AI) has been making significant strides in recent years, and one area where it is poised to make a considerable impact is in the realm of contextual search. Contextual search is a type of search that takes into account not only the keywords entered by the user but also the context in which those keywords are used. This means that the search engine will consider factors such as the user's location, search history, and even the time of day when determining which results to display. By taking into account above mentioned features, contextual search aims to provide users with more relevant and personalized search results².

One of the key benefits of AI-driven contextual search is its ability to provide users with personalized search results. The contextual awareness, that such engines are starting to integrate, embodies all the subtle nuances of human learning. It is the 'who', 'where', 'when', and 'why' that inform human decisions and behavior³. In a real-world conversation a simple query, "How is Grandma?", could elicit any number of potential responses depending on contextual factors, including time, circumstance, relationship, etc. Humans have an excellent communication process for conveying ideas to each other and reacting appropriately. This is due to many factors: the richness of the language they share, the common understanding of how the world works and an implicit understanding of everyday situations. In this

¹ https://www.ita-airways.com/en_en

² AI and the Future of Contextual Search: An In-depth Analysis: <https://ts2.space/en/ai-and-the-future-of-contextual-search-an-in-depth-analysis/>

³ Advancing Machine Intelligence: Why Context Is Everything: <https://towardsdatascience.com/advancing-machine-intelligence-why-context-is-everything-4bde90fb2d79>

sense, the next generation of search engines can also be regarded as recommended systems; sets of tools and techniques to provide useful recommendations and suggestions to the users to help them in the decision-making process for choosing the right products or services⁴.

With some notable exceptions, however, most Machine Learning (ML) models used for recommender systems incorporate very limited context of a specific query, relying primarily on the generic context provided by the data-set that the model is trained or fine-tuned on⁵. As a result, also most traditional recommender systems, such as those based on content-based and collaborative filtering, tend to use fairly simple user models, based on vectors of vector of item ratings⁶. In other words, the traditional systems observe mostly two types of entities, users and items, and do not put them into a context when providing recommendations^{7, 8, 9}. In applications domains, such as the recommendation in eCommerce¹⁰, personalization of content in web sites¹¹, and travel¹² and restaurant recommendation¹³, it is not sufficient to consider only information about users and items, and the context-independent representation may lead to lose predictive power since potentially useful information from multiple contexts is aggregated in a relatively static user-model. Furthermore, such approaches also raise significant concerns about bias which makes them less suited for use in many business, healthcare, and other critical applications. By taking into account factors such as a user's search history, location, activity, company of people, intent (e.g., causal lunch, business dinner, or anniversary) and user preferences, AI can tailor the search results to better meet the user's needs. This not only makes it easier for users to find the information they are looking for but also helps to improve the overall user experience.

In OWS we intend to adapt and implement a contextual post-filtering approach, in which the *Location-Aware* part of the index and *Collaborative Filtering* (i.e. basic user preferences) are used to generate the first series, i.e. top-N of possibilities in the area. The concept of *Contextual Post-Filtering*, applied at the edge, is then used to adjust the ranking and further filter-out the recommendations, personalized to the user's contextual information. The goal of the application is to demonstrate how the Open Index can be exploited to create a privacy preserving user-centric application.

⁴ Raza, S., & Ding, C. (2019). Progress in context-aware recommender systems—An overview. *Computer Science Review*, 31, 84-97.

⁵ Yasunaga, M., Ren, H., Bosselut, A., Liang, P., & Leskovec, J. (2021). QA-GNN: Reasoning with language models and knowledge graphs for question answering. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.06378*.

⁶ Kulkarni, S., & Rodd, S.F. (2020). Context Aware Recommendation Systems: A review of the state of the art techniques. *Computer Science Review*, 37

⁷ Nawara, D., & Kashef, R. (2022, April). Context-aware recommendation systems using consensus-clustering. In *2022 IEEE International Systems Conference (SysCon)* (pp. 1-8). IEEE.

⁸ Adomavicius, G., Bauman, K., Tuzhilin, A., & Unger, M. (2021). Context-Aware Recommender Systems: From Foundations to Recent Developments Context-aware recommender systems. In *Recommender Systems Handbook* (pp. 211-250). New York, NY: Springer US.

⁹ Ramirez-Garcia, X., & García-Valdez, M. (2014). Post-filtering for a restaurant context-aware recommender system. *Recent advances on hybrid approaches for designing intelligent systems*, 695-707.

¹⁰ Karimova, F. (2016). A survey of e-commerce recommender systems. *European Scientific Journal*, 12(34), 75-89.

¹¹ Martinez, L., Calles, J., & Martin, E. (2010). Ontology-based Web service to recommend spare time activities. In: *International Workshop on Information Heterogeneity and Fusion in Recommender Systems (HetRec)*, Barcelona.

¹² Chaudhari, K., & Thakkar, A. (2020). A comprehensive survey on travel recommender systems. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 27, 1545-1571.

¹³ Al-Ghuribi, S. M., & Noah, S. A. M. (2019). Multi-criteria review-based recommender system—the state of the art. *IEEE Access*, 7, 169446-169468.

2.4 Conversational Search

With the rise of large language models (LLMs) for generative information retrieval (IR), a new search paradigm in the form of conversations between searchers and systems has become increasingly popular. In contrast to traditional search result pages containing ten blue links, the new paradigm rather means to show an automatically generated text summarizing (and possibly referencing) the top search results. Our concern is that this development entails the risk of advertisements being incorporated directly (in the form of brand or product placements) in the generated answers, similar to native advertising. Since advertising is a multi-billion dollar business and the main source of revenue for search engines, it seems unlikely that this opportunity to earn money will be missed in generative IR. From a user's perspective, this potential form of advertising is highly critical since it could make recognizing advertisements way more challenging than before. To raise awareness for this issue, we have conducted a preliminary study (submitted to OSSYM 2023¹⁴) in which we explore the capability of current LLMs to blend advertisements with generated search result summaries. In one scenario, we prompted GPT4¹⁵ and YouChat¹⁶ with text snippets on a given topic and asked them to integrate subtle mentions or advertisements for a specific brand unrelated to the topic. In a second scenario, we let the models choose suitable brands to be promoted in texts about more general topics. An analysis of human assessments of the resulting responses shows that ads are difficult to include in an unrelated context and that more convincing ads can be created for brands closer to a given topic. We plan to further extend our analyses and aim at developing approaches to identify this potential form of advertising as well as approaches to counteract it, like a new kind of ad blocker for native advertising. The goal is to provide tools for more trustworthy and transparent environments in conversational search.

2.5 Intent Analysis

Internet analysis is a special case of Personal search. Geographic relevance is defined as “a relation between a geographic information need” (like an attention span) and “the spatio-temporal expression of the geographic information objects needed to satisfy it” (like an area of influence). Geographic information can be classified according to categories or topics, but it can be also classified by user intent. Hassan et al. (2009)¹⁷ underline the importance of the information about the location that could be helpful to filter the results on the most relevant items for the user. Our aim is to classify the geographic information not only by topics but also by user intent so that the user can get the best results while searching for the geographic information. Different types of user intent such as “find a location”, “give an address of a location” can give insights to the system, so that it can provide the best answers. Also, for various types of user intent, techniques such a named entity recognition and geocoding would help to identify the most useful information for the searcher.

3. Transparency and trust concept

¹⁴ <https://opensearchfoundation.org/ossym2023>

¹⁵ <https://openai.com/index/gpt-4/>

¹⁶ <https://web.youchat.com/>

¹⁷ Hassan, A., Juahir, H., & Jamaludin, N. S. (2009). The level of environmental awareness among students to fulfill the aspiration of national philosophy of education. *American Journal of Scientific Research*, 5, 50-58

This section elaborates on the concepts of trust and transparency in the context of open web search, as well as their relation to each others. First, theoretical and psychological considerations based on a literature study is presented. Second, a model is presented that intends to increase informed trust based on web search transparency. This model is basis for user studies, that investigate details on trust and transparency.

3.1 Theoretical background

Despite the broad literature background in the area of trust, this multi-faceted concept expands in meaning and definitions, especially since the increased usage of search engines, artificial intelligence (AI) and digital tools in general. Therefore, the concept of trust results in more complex meanings and even more definitions, often depending on the discipline defining the concept (e.g. psychology, economics, sociology and ethics) and on the object that needs to be trusted (e.g. search engines, search results, platforms, organizations etc.). For this work, trust in search engines and search results with a focus on search applications is relevant with the goal to increase trust of the user in the general use of the OWI and emerging applications.

Several studies show that users actually have a lot of trust in search engines^{18, 19, 20} and their appraisal of search engines are more often positive than negative²¹. Furthermore, people trust their search engine to list the most relevant results for what they are looking for and they rely on these information. While the trust in search engines in general seems to be high, knowledge about the functionality of search engines and business models is rather low. There is also a correlation between actual knowledge and trust. People who are able to identify mechanisms like paid search marketing and search engine organisation tend to have lower levels of trust. However, there often is a big difference between actual knowledge and perceived knowledge, as people tend to overestimate themselves^{22, 23} and people with less actual knowledge are less able to accurately estimate their own knowledge, which is a common and well-known effect in psychology called the Dunning-Kruger-effect²⁴. In align with this, search users are overall very confident in their perceived search abilities. This means that people might often not be aware of their lack of knowledge and, in general, they tend to overestimate their capabilities, which, in the searching process, can lead to uninformed decision-making.

The investigation of underlying reasons why people have so much trust in search engines is under-represented in current research. As mentioned above, when people tend to overestimate their own

¹⁸ Pan, B., Hembrooke, H., Joachims, T., Lorigo, L., Gay, G., & Granka, L. (2007). In google we trust: Users' decisions on rank, position, and relevance. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 12(3), 801–823. doi:10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00351.x

¹⁹ Purcell, K., Brenner, J., & Rainie, L. (2012). Search engine use 2012. Washington, DC. https://www.eff.org/files/pew_2012_0.pdf (accessed 03 August 2023).

²⁰ Schultheiß, S., Sünkler, S., & Lewandowski, D. (2018). We still trust in Google, but less than 10 years ago: an eye-tracking study. *Information Research*, 23(3), paper 799.

²¹ Schultheiß, S., & Lewandowski, D. (2023). Misplaced trust? The relationship between trust, ability to identify commercially influenced results and search engine preference. *Journal of Information Science*, 49(3), 609–623. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515211014157>

²² Alicke, M. D., & Govorun, O. (2005). The better-than-average effect. In *The self in social judgment* (pp. 86–106).

²³ Guenther, C. L., & Alicke, M. D. (2010). Deconstructing the Better-Than-Average Effect. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 99(5), 755–770. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0020959> .

²⁴ Kruger, J., & Dunning, D. (1999). Unskilled and unaware of it: How difficulties in recognizing one's own incompetence lead to inflated self-assessments. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 77(6), 1121–1134. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.77.6.1121>

search-abilities (and they do even more when they have little actual knowledge), there might be little concerns about whether to trust search engines or not. Furthermore, people use trust mechanisms in the process of decision-making. In uncertain situations people tend to reduce the complexity of the decision making, which can be achieved by trusting.

Nevertheless, there are a number of reasons why unquestioned and uninformed trust in search engines might not be justified. For example, search results can be manipulated, user data can be reused for commercial purposes, or social biases can have influence on the search result.

The concept of transparency is often linked to trust, because it is often suggested that a lack of transparency leads to biases on the technological side like biased selection criteria of search results^{25,26,27}. Therefore, there are suggestions that higher transparency would minimize these problems and lead to higher trust. However, the relation between trust and transparency is not clarified through literature. Shin and Park²⁸, for example, argue that trust itself has a moderating effect on transparency (and other related concepts like satisfaction and accountability). To our knowledge, current literature is lacking a theoretical framework, that describes the relation between trust and transparency.

A definition of the transparency concept is needed for both a theoretical framework on trust and transparency, as well as for deriving practical implications in search engines. Shin and Park (2019) consider transparency consisting of three components, namely understandability, explainability, and observability. These components can be considered in the design of a user interface that supports transparency.

The future work and next steps include both theoretical and empirical work on the trust and transparency concepts related to search engines. Since there is a lack of knowledge on the relation between trust and transparency in literature, user studies will be conducted that will investigate transparency factors that lead to increased trust. The next section outlines an initial transparency concept that will be investigated related to trust. This concept will be used as basis for the planned empirical studies.

3.2 Transparency model

In recent years, search engines have become important in a lot of aspects of our daily lives. Current web search engines are operated by a few gatekeepers that are often focused on commercial success, which results in limited and manipulated information access, barely taking into account societal and ethical values. Furthermore, the emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) added an extreme amount of AI-generated disinformation to the Web, which makes it very difficult to adequately determine which sources and messages can be trusted. Additionally, current search engines are black boxes, lacking transparency in their behavior, data collection, and algorithms. Despite these problems, search engine users place a lot of trust in search engines, while knowledge about the functionality and underlying mechanisms is rather low. This circumstance can lead to biased or uninformed decision-making.

²⁵ Epstein, R., & Robertson, R. E. (2015). The search engine manipulation effect (SEME) and its possible impact on the outcomes of elections. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(33), E4512-E4521. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1419828112>

²⁶ Pariser, E. (2011). *The Filter Bubble: What the internet is hiding from you*. Penguin Books.

²⁷ van Hoboken, J. (2012). *Search engine freedom: On the implications of the right to freedom of expression for the legal governance of web search engines*. https://pure.uva.nl/ws/files/1769429/104098_thesis.pdf

²⁸ Shin, D., & Park, Y. J. (2019). Role of fairness, accountability, and transparency in algorithmic affordance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 98, 277–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.04.019>

Therefore, a trust and transparency concept has been elaborated that encourages and supports transparency features of search applications that emerge from the OWI in order to overcome aforementioned issues. The goal of this concept is to promote transparency and adequate trust in Web search. To achieve these goals, we created a transparency framework to provide guidelines for search application developers and to increase adequate trust of the end-user.

For the development of this concept, a review of existing literature in the context of trust and transparency in Web search was conducted (see D4.2). After that, we followed a qualitative approach, conducting 3 focus groups.

In the first focus group, 4 participants reflected on the following questions:

- Which search engines and search applications am I using?
- What do I use search applications for?
- How often do I use search applications?

After that, aspects of trust and transparency in the context of search applications were discussed, reflecting on the following research questions:

- Why do people trust (the results of) search applications?
- What do you need to trust search applications as a user?
- How do you define a “transparent search application”?
- What aspects need to be made transparent in search applications?
- Is there a connection between trust and transparency in search applications?

Based on existing literature and the insights gained from the first focus group, we developed a first version of a transparency concept and defined relevant transparency aspects (What should be made transparent in a search application?) and possible ways to make these aspects transparent in a search application (How can these aspects be made transparent in a search application?).

The second focus group reflected on the same questions mentioned above. Furthermore, an evaluation of the identified transparency categories and mechanisms was added. Based on the insights from the second focus group, the concept was adapted again and evaluated by a group of experts in a third focus group with 4 participants.

All these gained insights from the focus groups served as a basis for the development and the resulting final version of the transparency concept that is described in the following: We identified 27 relevant issues and questions related to trust and transparency in Web search and categorized them into three categories:

- **(a) general information on Web search**
- **(b) specific search application**
- **(c) presented search results: content characteristics.**

To address these relevant issues in search applications, we identified four specific methods:

- **(1) Explanation** relates to giving information by explaining and providing information with general or specific explanations.
- **(2) Exploration** relates to the user-interaction with the application and the possibility to control the search process (e.g. through filter options).

- **(3) Processed data** relates to providing additional useful information from analyzed content data.
- **(4) (Self-)Reflection** promotes critical thinking, digital information literacy skills and a mindful interaction with search tools.

This concept is implemented in a questionnaire for developers (see next subsection), where the search application developers answer all the questions regarding the search application themselves. After answering a specific transparency question, the developer can categorize the answers into a suitable method described above (Explanation, Exploration, Processed data, (Self-)Reflection), if possible, or define the method as “Other”, if no proposed method is suitable.

An example for this can be seen in Figure 1. This depicted question derives from the category of “search results: content characteristics” and wants the developer to answer if there is some kind of available information on the topic of the presented search result. In this example, this aspect “Topic” is addressed in a way that the title of a publication and parts of the abstract of the respective result are presented on the result page. The method used for answering this question is “processed data”, since there are additional algorithms necessary to extract this information from the original page, e.g. to summarize a text, identify the title, keywords etc.

Topic

What is the information/are the messages about (e.g. topic extraction, text summary, keywords)?

The method how this question is addressed:

Processed Data

Description: some parts of the article/abstract, including the title are listed, that often include the searched keyword

Figure 1: Example of a question on the transparency for the application developer

3.3. Guideline for application developers

Questionnaire on transparency and trust
<p>Thank you for choosing to work with our transparency concept!</p> <p>The aim of this concept is to make relevant aspects, linked to transparency and trust, transparent to the end user and therefore making the application more transparent and trustworthy as well. We want to promote adequate trust in applications and the presented search results and encourage application developers to reflect their very own application in the context of trustworthiness and transparency.</p>

In the following, you will find questions that are linked to trust and transparency on the web in general, on your search application and the presented results themselves. There are different possible ways and methods to address these questions, which are described below.

1. Explanation means giving information by providing information with general or specific explanations and descriptions.
2. Exploration means the user-interaction with the application and the possibility to individually control the search process (e.g. through filter options).
3. Process-data means providing additional information to the user from specific analyzed data.
4. Self-reflection in this scenario means promoting and encouraging critical thinking and digital information literacy skills as well as a mindful interaction with search applications.

It is not necessary to have all the questions answered at once. If you see a question you did not address but find important as well, maybe you will find ways to address them in your application later on and you can add these information into the following matrix any time. With your help we will provide you with a transparency label, which can be made visible on your application and shows the extent of transparency of your application.

To fill out the following form, think about the questions and if you addressed them in your application, add the used method or methods (also more than one method is possible) by selecting it in the form and use the blank field to describe shortly how you addressed the question (you could add links, explanations, examples etc.).

There are recommended methods for every question highlighted in blue, but you can also choose to use another method, if you find it reasonable and appropriate or you could use a completely different method as well. If you can not associate your answer with either of the proposed methods, just select "Other". If you did not address the question at all, select "Not addressed".

General search	Explan.	Explor.	Proc. data	Refl.
Functionality: How does a search engine work? Description:				
Financing: How are search engines financed? Description:				
Concerns: What are possible problems with search (engines and applications)? Description:				
Results: How can search results be filtered, ranked and presented? Description:				
Privacy: Which personal data can be collected/used/saved and why? Description:				
Search application	Explan.	Explor.	Proc. data	Refl.
Responsibility: Who created, owns and operates this search application? Description:				
Purpose: What is this search application about? Description:				
Functionality: How does this search application work?				

Description:				
Financing: How is this search application financed? Description:				
User feedback: Is there user feedback (e.g. rating, recommendation) or user created data (e.g. forum) and how is the quality assured? Description:				
Concerns: What are possible technical, ethical and societal concerns about this search application and how are they addressed? Description:				
Advertisement: How are advertisements and non-organic/paid search results displayed? Description:				
Results: How are search results created, filtered, ranked and presented? Description:				
Privacy: Which personal data is collected/used/saved and why? Description:				
Languages: How are languages integrated in the application? Description:				
Search results	Explan.	Explor.	Proc. data	Refl.
Responsibility: Who is responsible for the external content (e.g. website owner, publisher)? Description:				
Date: Is temporal information available (e.g. creation date, latest update)? Description:				
Topic: What is the information/are the messages about (e.g. topic extraction, text summary, keywords)? Description:				
Language: Which language is used? Description:				
Structure: Is information about the content structure available (e.g. media form, text style)? Description:				
Origin: What are the sources and references of the content? Description:				
Comparison: How does this compare to other messages/products/information and sources on this topic? Description:				
Dubious content: Is problematic content (e.g. spam, phishing, adult content, hate speech) labeled? Description:				

<p>Trustworthiness: Is this a trustworthy source about this topic and how might this information be confirmed?</p> <p>Description:</p>				
<p>Finances: Who paid for this? Who might make money from this and how?</p> <p>Description:</p>				
<p>Reaction: What kinds of actions might users take in response to this and how might different people interpret this differently?</p> <p>Description:</p>				

3.4. Transparency label

Every single answer from the developer is then added into a **transparency label**, which is the result of this questionnaire and can be described as a depiction of the extent of addressed questions (see Figure 2). Furthermore, this chart is interactive with the possibility for users to click on every aspect and directly see the answers given by the developer. On the one hand, the label should make it easier to see the overall extent of transparency at first glance. This makes it possible to compare applications in their extent of transparency. On the other hand, if wanted, because of the interactive usage, the label can be explored further and in a qualitative way as well. In the following, you can see a practical example of a transparency label that resulted from a completed questionnaire. Addressed issues are highlighted in colour, while issues that are not addressed are grey.

Figure 2: Transparency label on the example of Google scholar

On the application developer side, with this concept, reflection on trust and transparency-related issues is promoted by reflecting the transparency of their own search applications. Furthermore, developers

are encouraged to address more issues in their application and are being rewarded for it, since it can directly be depicted in the resulting transparency label.

On the end-user side, adequate trust is promoted in two ways. First, the addressing of the questions or issues of each category by the application developers leads to transparent information about the search application and the search results. Second, the illustration of the transparency label provides an overview of the transparency level of the application and serves as a basis that can be used to compare various search applications regarding their transparency.

To test the overall usability, the concept has been applied in different use cases. One use-case was the application “Google Scholar”, which enables users to search for publications, and other research. In this case, the answers were not given by the application developers themselves, but by a member of the working group to give an example of an often used and well-known application. The overall concept with the categories, respective questions, answers, and the resulting transparency label for Google Scholar can be explored here: <https://qnode.eu/ows/transparencylabel/>

4. Privacy and recommendation concept

In an age where the Internet is simply an indispensable part of life, the use of a search engine is possibly at the foundation of the user experience. The instantaneous access to information is not simply a ‘nice to have’ for researchers. It became the bedrock of our modern consumer -society. At the same time privacy became a significant issue in this age of information (see also deliverable D6.1). Activities that were once private or shared with the few now leave trails of data that expose our interests, traits, beliefs, and intentions. We communicate using e-mails, texts, and social media; find partners on dating sites; learn via online courses; seek responses to mundane and sensitive questions using search engines; read news and books in the cloud; navigate streets with geotracking systems; and celebrate our newborns, and mourn our dead, on social media profiles. Through these and other activities, we reveal information - both knowingly and unwittingly - to one another, to commercial entities, and to our governments. It is not only Google, all players in the search engine space, such as Microsoft’s Bing, Yahoo Search and Baidu, are mining consumer data. Of course search engines offer an essential service, however, that service is certainly not free of cost. The cost is a certain level of intrusion into our lives in the form of search engine companies like Google gathering data about our online habits and using that data to fine tune marketing efforts (often by selling that data to third parties for their use), but also benefits from inferring user habits and interests.

The main issue evolves around awareness and permission. Namely, “Are search engine companies free to gather and use our data without explicit permission - can we opt out of such an arrangement?”. The cornerstones of OWS end-user application will be a privacy framework built around trust, awareness and permission.

4.1 Privacy-preserving mechanisms

Privacy commonly relates to the meaning that sensitive information about individuals or groups is not disclosed to others. Although privacy and confidentiality are overlapped in some contexts, they appear somewhat different, in terms of their concepts and protection methods²⁹. Loss of confidentiality is mostly caused by the weakness of access control or encryption schemes, while loss of privacy is associated

²⁹ Tran, H. Y., & Hu, J. (2019). Privacy-preserving big data analytics a comprehensive survey. *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, 134, 207-218.

with not only that but also the vulnerabilities in the control of data utilization and data analytics (leading to linking attacks, inference attacks, etc.). Privacy-preserving protection methods take into account the utility of data besides the protection of privacy. Confidentiality is realized primarily by encryption and access control. Cryptography is also utilized to preserve privacy in terms of keeping the data confidential. Besides cryptographic tools, privacy is also preserved by perturbation (to mask the true data value) and anonymization (to hide the 'data–data owner' links) techniques. Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology can further contribute to create a secure distributed ecosystem in which data can be used with the required permission.

4.1.1 Cryptography and Homomorphic Encryption

Cryptographic methods mostly employ Secure Multi-party Computation³⁰, delivered by some form of Homomorphic Encryption schemes^{31,32}. These methods preserve privacy by keeping private data items in encrypted forms, then performing utility functionalities on encrypted individual data items to get encrypted aggregate results, and finally decrypting these results to get the outputs of the same functionalities as if on plain individual data items.

An example would be preservation of the user location using Homomorphic Encryption. The user encrypts data with the public key before transferring it to the cloud. The cloud server can perform calculations and computations on the cipher text, but it cannot decrypt the results of the computations as it does not have the private key. The server responds the cipher text back to the user who can decrypt the results to get the desired results. Under a similar fashion one can encrypt any text-based query data³³. For trustworthy services, i.e. services where user's consent for their personalized data to be used, asymmetric cryptography can be exploited. Asymmetric cryptography uses a pair of keys for encryption and decryption. A public key is used for encryption and a private key is used for decryption. The messages encoded using public keys can only be decoded by trusted end-points which were assigned private keys.

Although cryptographic computation can guarantee "perfect" privacy in terms of keeping data confidential by the security strength of cryptographic primitives, the weaknesses are challenges in the scalability and implementation efficiency, which is mostly due to the high computational complexity of existing homomorphic encryption schemes.

A non-perturbative method preserves privacy by sanitizing identifiable information, thereby preventing identity from being connected with adversary's background information.

4.1.2 Obfuscation and perturbation

Obfuscation and data perturbation techniques use similar approaches. Among the perturbation approaches, Polat et al.³⁴ proposed hiding personal data statistically while generating

³⁰ Goldreich, O. (1998). Secure multi-party computation. Manuscript. Preliminary version, 78(110).

³¹ Pulido-Gaytan, B., Tchernykh, A., Cortés-Mendoza, J. M., Babenko, M., Radchenko, G., Avetisyan, A., & Drozdov, A. Y. (2021). Privacy-preserving neural networks with homomorphic encryption: C challenges and opportunities. *Peer-to-Peer Networking and Applications*, 14(3), 1666-1691.

³² Khedr, A., Gulak, G., & Vaikuntanathan, V. (2015). SHIELD: scalable homomorphic implementation of encrypted data-classifiers. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 65(9), 2848-2858.

³³ Wu, Q, He, K., & Chen X. (2020). Personalized Federated Learning for Intelligent IoT Applications: A Cloud-Edge Based Framework. *IEEE Open Journal of the Computer Society*, 1, pp. 35–44. Doi: 10.1109/OJCS.2020.2993259

³⁴ Polat, H, & Du, W. (2005). SVD-based collaborative filtering with privacy. In: *Proceedings of the 2005 ACM Symposium on Applied Computing*, pp. 791–795. doi: 10.1145/1066677.1066860

recommendations, which were later, proved insecure³⁵. Shokri et al.³⁶ proposed a distributed obfuscation-based CF technique by allowing local user profile modifications while hiding the real profile from an untrusted central server. However, this approach requires trading-off between privacy and recommendation accuracy³⁷.

4.1.2 Differential privacy

The main idea behind the differential privacy is that a differentially private recommended result is not sensitive to any single user. Thus, it is a perfect notion to prevent the inference attack (e.g. on a recommender system). If a user's once purchase of an item does not cause an obvious change of a recommended list to that item, an attacker could not guess the purchased item with a high confidence just by observing the change of the output. In most systems differential privacy is achieved by adding noise to hide user data. For instance, McSherry et al.³⁸ address the privacy issue in recommender systems using Laplace noise. They add Laplace noise to the movie average rating, user average rating and covariance matrix. Then the noisy matrices are released and used in the current recommender algorithm. Moritz Hardt et al.³⁹ convert the recommendation problem into the Matrix Completion problem, which tries to recover the missing entries of a matrix under a partially given matrix with a subset of the entries are randomly sampled.

4.2 Prototype of Privacy preserving Personalized Search

As implemented in the first pilot of the Privacy-preserving Location-based Restaurant Recommender system (see D4.1), we treat Personalized Search as a contextually aware recommendation system. Since recommenders operate by processing, collecting and analyzing numerous user data, serious privacy concerns are raised. To at least partially mitigate these concerns the idea in OWS is to a) separate the contextual awareness aspect of the search from its user matching aspect and b) implement the recommender, using distributed recommender and a homomorphic encryption scheme. The concept is outlined in Figure 3.

³⁵ Zhang, S., Ford, J., & Makedon, F. (2006). Deriving Private Information from Randomly Perturbed Ratings. In: Proceedings of the 2006 SIAM International Conference on Data Mining (SDM), pp. 59-69. doi:10.1137/1.9781611972764.6.

³⁶ Shokri, R., Pedarsani, P. & Theodorakopoulos, G., & Hubaux, J.-P. (2009). Preserving privacy in collaborative filtering through distributed aggregation of offline profiles. In Proceedings of the third ACM conference on Recommender systems. ACM, pp. 157–164.

³⁷ Badsha, S., Yi, X., Khalil, I., & Bertino, E. (2017, June). Privacy preserving user-based recommender system. In 2017 IEEE 37th international conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS) (pp. 1074-1083). IEEE.

³⁸ McSherry F, Mironov I. (2009). Differentially private recommender systems: Building privacy into the Netflix Prize contenders. In Proceedings of the 15th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining (KDD '09), pp. 627-636. ACM:New York, NY, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1557019.1557090>

³⁹ Hardt, M. & Roth, A. (2012). Beating randomized response on incoherent matrices. In Proceedings of the forty-fourth annual ACM symposium on Theory of computing (STOC '12). Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 1255–1268. New York, NY, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2213977.2214088>

data such as preferred restaurants (based on clicked items), time of day, and even calendar events, like upcoming business meetings, to tailor recommendations to the user's immediate needs. The app also analyzes user ratings and comments to extract sentiment, refining its suggestions based on likes and dislikes. These contextual factors—time, preferences, and feedback—help the app evolve and offer more relevant recommendations, whether it's for lunch, dinner, or a specific occasion.

The core principle of the app is to protect user privacy while providing personalized recommendations. All sensitive data stays on the user's device, and only a minimalistic, complemented query is sent to the server to ensure relevant suggestions are made. This query contains just the essential information necessary for recommendations, without exposing user habits, personal events, or specific preferences. By balancing personalization with privacy, the app ensures that users receive a highly tailored experience without compromising their data security.

Figure 4: Architecture of privacy preserving contextual model of user habits.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

This deliverable presents an updated set of privacy, transparency and trust models that support the development of search applications using the OWS infrastructure. Together with technical aspects and demonstrations on how to develop search applications in deliverable D4.1, it provides a holistic grounding for the development of search applications.

The future work will focus on the refinement and application of the models in search applications. In user-centred evaluations their effect and acceptance will be tested and accordingly updated. The final versions and results from the evaluation will be presented in the deliverable D4.4.

Appendix

See included the list of Acronyms and Abbreviations used in OWS context.

Acronym / Abbreviation	Term
AR	Augmented Reality
ML	Machine Learning
OSSYM	Open Search Symposium
OWI	Open Web Index
OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project